

**3D MODELING OF SUPPLY IN THE SOFTWARE PACKAGE
AUTODESK 3DS MAX**

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Abstract. The main issue of the study is the problem of the possibility and feasibility of 3D modeling, and the use of supply and exhaust systems for heat and moisture recovery in the design of a passive building, using a 2-stage scheme of air heating in climatic and geographical conditions. After all, using this mechanical ventilation and air heating scheme in a passive building, it is possible to reduce annual energy costs by 3-4 times. The higher capital costs of a passive building are offset by lower operating costs due to a significant reduction in energy consumption.

Keywords: 3ds MAX, modeling, system, cost, energy.

INTRODUCTION

The actual problem is to reduce the cost of maintenance of engineering systems of buildings and structures. Such costs include the transportation of energy resources from source to consumer, the complexity of heat supply systems due to the large number of equipment, and as a consequence, the presence of excessive heat losses. One of the solutions is the construction of buildings that meet modern energy efficiency requirements. [1-6]

MAIN PART

This article discusses a set of parameters that contribute to the implementation of the concept of "Passive building". Application of mechanical supply and exhaust ventilation as an alternative production of thermal energy for the heat supply system (fig. 1). The main characteristics for heat and moisture recovery systems are

established. It is revealed that the costs of heating and air conditioning will not exceed the set maximum [2].

Figure 1. 3D modeling of air ducts supply and exhaust ventilation, in the software package Autodesk3ds Max.

The implementation of energy efficiency measures can significantly reduce the amount of energy spent on utilities. Energy-saving effect is achieved due to the total architectural, construction and engineering solutions aimed at saving energy. At the engineering design stage, we achieve energy efficiency through the following recommendations [3]:

- Ventilation of premises organized by mechanical supply and exhaust ventilation with stimuli of movement of supply and exhaust air with obligatory use of heat of exhaust air on heating of supply external air (application of installation of utilization allows to reduce heat consumption on heating and ventilation of the passive building to 61,3% in one step); [4]

- For use in Windows of thermally insulated energy-saving triple glazing with two low- emission coatings and filling with inert gas. In such a double-glazed window there are two chambers with inert gas filling, and two low-emission coatings. The heat transfer coefficient is: $k = 0.5 \text{ W} / \text{m}^2 * \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$;

- Increasing the thickness of the insulation in excess of minimum sanitary standards in 4-5 times.

The energy efficiency indicator of the facility is the amount of heat energy consumed [4] per square meter (kWh / m²) during the year or during the heating period. In a passive building, the index does not exceed 15 kWh / m² [5].

Installation of supply and exhaust ventilation with heat and moisture recovery helps to achieve a comfortable microclimate. This system humidifies the air to the sanitary standard that is needed in an urban setting. [4] to significantly reduce the ever-increasing demand for energy, it is necessary to use different approaches that limit its consumption. It is necessary to reduce heat loss. Only a combination of several solutions gives a rational economy. [5]

The purpose of this study is the possibility and feasibility of using heat and moisture recovery systems in the design of passive buildings in climatic and geographical conditions for the city in this climatic zone.

To achieve this goal it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- Determine the optimal location in the space of a given geographical location;
- Identify technical solutions to reduce energy consumption;

Heat loss of the building, taking into account the 2-stage scheme of air heating (fig. 2) in the ventilation system and additional insulation of the enclosing structures will amount to 13.565 kWh / m², then the energy efficiency index will not exceed 15 kWh / m², therefore the building will be passive.

Figure 2. 3D modeling of supply and exhaust ventilation 2-stage scheme of air heating, in the software package Autodesk 3ds Max.

CONCLUSION

It is economically advantageous that the costs for the life cycle of a passive building, i.e. the total cost of design, construction, operation for 30 years [6], will not exceed the costs for the life cycle of a traditional residential building. Higher capital costs of a passive building are offset by lower operating costs due to a significant reduction in energy consumption [3].

Summarizing the work done, using a 2-step scheme of air heating in the concept of a passive building, in the city of this climatic zone, it is possible to create conditions for more profitable energy savings.

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